

Kırgız Okuyucuların Kırgız İnternet Medyasında Kullanılan Taklit Olgularına Yönelik Algısı

Kyrgyz Readers' Perception of Precedent Phenomena Used in Kyrgyz Internet Media

Altynai TOKTOMATOVA¹

1. Dr., Kırgızistan-Türkiye Manas Üniversitesi, Yabancı Diller Yüksekokulu, Yabancı Diller Bölümü, altynai.toktomatova@manas.edu.kg

2. Okutman, Kırgızistan-Türkiye Manas Üniversitesi, Yabancı Diller Yüksekokulu, Dil Hazırlık Bölümü, saliya.vayskanova@manas.edu.kg

Öz

Çalışma, Kırgızistan'ın internet medyasında evrensel ve ulusal taklit olgularının temsilini analiz etmektedir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, evrensel ve ulusal taklit olgularının medyada nasıl yansıtıldığını ve Kırgız okuyucular tarafından nasıl algılandığını göstermektir. Araştırmada, internet gazetelerinde gazeteciler tarafından kullanılan ulusal ve evrensel taklit olgularının Kırgız toplumunun sıradan temsilcileri tarafından bilinip bilinmediğine de değinilmeye çalışılmıştır. Hedeflenen amaca ulaşmak için son on yılda yayınlanan internet medya içerikleri incelenmiştir. Super.kg gibi bilgi-eğlence portalından bbc.com gibi dünyanın önde gelen yayın kuruluşuna kadar birçok ünlü internet medyası incelemeye alınmıştır. Ardından, dört farklı türde ulusal ve evrensel taklit olgusunu içeren sekiz metin parçası seçilmiştir. Yapısal bir anket, çeşitli WhatsApp gruplarına dağıtılmıştır. 100 kişilik katılımcı tarafından doldurulan anketin sonuçlarından yola çıkarak araştırmanın bulguları oluşturulmuştur. Tanımlayıcı, çevrimiçi anket ve veri analizi yöntemleri, belirlenen hedeflere ulaşmak için kullanılmıştır. Çalışmaya dâhil edilen ulusal ve evrensel katmandaki üç taklit olgusunun %50'nin altında olması, taklit olgularının sadece sözlüksel birimler değil, olgusal, aksiyolojik ve değerlendirici bileşenlerden oluşan zihni yapılar olduğunu kanıtlamaktadır. Bununla birlikte, yine de pek çok şey muhatapların arka plan bilgisine ve bilişsel temeline bağlıdır. Taklit fenomenlerin karmaşık doğasının dikkate alınması ve bilişsel dilbilim, dil-kültür çalışmaları, metin ve söylem teorisi gibi birçok disiplin içerisinde incelenmesi gerektiği sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kırgız İnternet Medyası, Kırgız Okuyucular, Taklit Olgusu, Taklit Metin, Taklit İfade ve Durumlar

Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the universal and national precedent phenomena representation in the Kyrgyz internet media. The purpose of the paper is to show how universal and national precedent phenomena are represented in the media and perceived by Kyrgyz readers. An attempt is made to point out if the national and universal precedent phenomena used by journalists in online newspapers are known to ordinary representatives of the Kyrgyz community. To reach the purpose put forward, Internet media contents published over the last ten years were studied. Many popular Internet media, ranging from information-entertainment portals like super.kg to the world's leading public service broadcasters like bbc.com were investigated. Eight text fragments that included four different kinds of national and universal precedent phenomena were then chosen. A structured questionnaire was distributed to various WhatsApp groups. Based on the survey results filled out by 100 respondents, the findings were developed. Descriptive, online survey and data analysis methods were employed to achieve the stated goals. The fact that the three precedent phenomena of national and universal layers included in the survey got less than 50% proves that precedent phenomena are not just lexical units but mental constructs consisting of factual, axiological, and evaluative components. Still, a lot depends on the background knowledge and cognitive base of the recipients. It can be concluded that the complex nature of precedent phenomena should be taken into consideration, and they should be studied within many disciplines like cognitive linguistics, linguacultural studies, and text and discourse theory.

Keywords: Kyrgyz Internet Media, Kyrgyz Readers, Precedent Phenomena, Precedent Text, Precedent Statement and Situations

Araştırma Makalesi Research Article

10.5281/
zenodo.10416952

Geliş/Received: 09.11.2023

Kabul/Accepted: 25.12.2023

Yayın/Published: 30.12.2023

OPEN ACCESS

buranadergisi.com

Introduction

In the modern world, precedent phenomena are quite common in the speech of many people. Precedent phenomena are widely used in media by journalists to embellish their speech. Perception of social, national and universal precedent phenomena is included in cognitive base of readers since the sources of precedent phenomena are stories, novels or fairy tales (names of the characters, titles and quotes), historical figures, statements of the popular politicians, aphorisms, names of the popular anecdote characters, names of mythological heroes (Apollo, Achilles, Hector, Hercules, Ariadne, etc.), film titles, slogans, advertising slogans, quotes from songs, proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, folklore, situations that occurred in a particular society and when used in speech, the participants in the conversation understand what they are talking about.

1. Literature Review

Precedent text was first introduced by Yu. N. Karaulov (2010, p. 216) which was described “as (1) significant for a person in cognitive and emotional terms, (2) have a superpersonal nature, i. e. are well known to the general environment of this person, along with his predecessors and contemporaries, and finally, such, (3) an appeal to which it is constant in the discourse of this linguistic personality”. This theory was further developed by famous scientists such as D. B. Gudkov, V. V. Krasnykh, I. V. Zakharenko, D. V. Bagaeva and many others and to describe the text introduced by Karaulov, a new term “precedent phenomena” was proposed by them. Precedent phenomena are divided into four: precedent names, precedent statements, precedent situation and precedent text.

A precedent name is an individual name associated either with a widely known text, usually classified as a precedent one (e.g., Manas, Akytkarachach), or with a situation that is well known to native speakers and acts as a precedent one (Ivan Susanin, Columbus), a name-symbol indicating a certain reference set of certain qualities (Chyngyz Aitmatov, Toktogul) (Gudkov, 2003, p. 108).

A precedent statement is a reproducible product of speech-thinking activity; a complete and self-sufficient unit that can be predicative or not; a complex sign, the sum of values of its components is not equal to its meaning; the cognitive base includes the precedent statement itself. Precedent statements include quotations from texts of various types, aphorisms, proverbs, and sayings (Krasnykh etc., 1997, p. 65).

A precedent situation is a certain “standard”, “ideal” situation associated with certain connotations that has ever existed in reality or belongs to the virtual reality of art created by man (man-made art); the cognitive base includes a set of differential features of PS, meaning PS can be a precedent statement or a precedent name, as well as a non-precedent phenomenon (Krasnykh, 2002, p. 45).

A precedent text is defined as “a complete and self-sufficient product of speech-thinking activity, a (poly) predicative unit; a complex sign, the sum of the values of its components is not equal to its meaning; PT is well known to any average member of the national-cultural community; its cognitive base includes an invariant of its perception; reference to PT is repeatedly renewed in the process of communication through precedent statements or symbols associated with this text” (Krasnykh etc., 1997, p. 64).

Four levels of precedent phenomena highlighted by Gudkov (2003, p. 103-104) are Self-precedents, Socio-precedent phenomena, National precedent phenomena and Universal precedent phenomena. Self-precedents are the reflection in the consciousness of a person of certain phenomena of the world around him, which have a special cognitive, emotional, axiological significance for this person, which is associated with special individual ideas involved in unique associative series. Socio-precedent phenomena are known to any ordinary representative of a particular society and are part of the collective cognitive space. Every society has a certain set of predecessors, unique to it. National precedent phenomena are known to any ordinary representative of a linguistic and cultural community and are part of the cognitive base of this community. Universal precedent phenomena are known to any modern full-fledged homo sapiens and are part of the universal cognitive space of mankind.

2. Materials and Methods of Research

Our purpose was to identify how people perceive national and universal precedent phenomena presented on the Internet media. First the authors studied Internet media content published for the last ten years. Such online newspapers as kadam-media.kg, sayasat.kg, sputnik.kg, kloop.asia, for.kg/news, super.kg and bbc.com were studied. Starting from the least official to the most official online newspapers covering national and international interests and news were investigated. Then 8 text fragments containing four types of precedent phenomena of national and universal layers were selected. A questionnaire was structured and the form was sent to different WhatsApp groups. After the form

was filled by 100 respondents, authors came up with their outcomes. To reach the purpose set forward descriptive, online survey and data analysis methods were used.

1. Ойлоп карасак, азыркы Робин Гуд болуп жаткандар баягы эле элден акча чогултуп жатат, элсом аркылуу... (If we look around, the current Robin Hoods are collecting money from ordinary people, through Elsom...) (Kyrgyz koomu özübüzdü emes, özgönü künöölöp köngön elbiz, 2022).

Robin is a famous folk hero who helped the poor and peasants who suffered because of oppressive forest laws. Because of forest law emitted by Normans many areas became depopulated, peasants had to move to other places. Native nobles fought against Norman tyranny and it was reflected in the folklore as Robin Hood.

2. КР Улуттук китепканасынын Сейрек кездешүүчү жана өзгөчө баалуу басылмалар бөлүмүнүн окуу залында 2019-жылдын 27 сентябрында “XX- кылымдын Гомери” аттуу Саякбай Каралаевдин туулган күнүнүн 125 жылдыгына карата китеп көргөзмөсү окурмандарга тартууланат. (On September 27, 2019, a book exhibition dedicated to the 125th anniversary of the birth of Sayakbai Karalaev called “Homer of XX century” will be presented to readers in the reading hall of the Rare and Specially Valuable Publications Department of the National Library of the Kyrgyz Republic) (20-kylymdun Gomeri, 2019).

Everybody knows that Homer was an outstanding Greek poet; the epic poems like Iliad and Odyssey written by him are the basic works of ancient literature. S. Karalaev is Homer of XX century is a direct quotation of a great Kyrgyz writer Ch. Aitmatov.

3. 2002-жылы “темир айымдын” ден-соолугу начарлап, отставкага кетип, коомдук жана саясий иш-чаралардан баш тартат. (In 2002, the “Iron Lady’s” health worsened, she resigned and refused to participate in social and political events) (“Temir ayim” Margaret Thatcher, 2013).

It’s widely known that the economic policies implemented by Margaret Thatcher, the first female prime minister of the 20th century, are referred to as Thatcherism. The nickname the “Iron Lady” associated with her politics and leadership style was given by a soviet journalist.

4. Ийилчээк «темир айым». Лиз Трасс – Британиянын премьер-министри. Улуу Британияда Консервативдик партиянын лидери болуп, демек өкмөт башчысы болуп Элизабет Трасс шайланды. Британдык жаңы “темир айым” болгусу келип жаткан Тори партиясынын 47 жаштагы саясатчысы салыктарды азайтып, Путиндин тизгинин тартарын убада кылууда. (Flexible “iron lady”. Liz Truss is the British Prime Minister. In Great Britain, Elizabeth Truss was elected as the leader of the Conservative Party, and therefore as the head of government. The 47-year-old Tory politician who wants to be Britain’s new “Iron Lady” promises to cut taxes and rein in Putin) (Iyilcheek temir ayim. Liz Truss – Britaniyanyn jany premier-ministri, 2022).

5. Ал эми быйылкы 31-августтагы эгемендик күнүндөгү желек көтөрүү салтанатында Алмаз Шаршенович жылдагы адатын андан ары улантып, “бер, бер эле дей бербей эл жалпы аракет кылышы керек. Ар бир адам өзүнө, мамлекет мага эмне кылып берди дебей, мен мамлекетке эмне кылып бердим деген суроону бериши керек” деп, митинг, пикеттен башы чыкпай жүргөн “кээ бир элдерди” өчү бардай дагы бир ирет зекип өттү. (And at the flag-raising ceremony on August 31 of this year, Almaz Sharshenovich continued his tradition of the year and reproached “some people” that they should make a concerted effort instead of just ‘asking.’ Everyone should, “ask not what your country can do for you...ask what you can do for your country”) (Eki жүздүүлүкпү je жүзү karalykpy?, 2012).

“My fellow Americans: ask not what your country can do for you - ask what you can do for your country.” was the part of John Kennedy’s inaugural speech that lasted for 14 minutes and best remembered. He did it on January 20, 1961.

6. ... мындан 111 жыл мурда кыргыз саясатында, дипломатиясында өз орду бар “Алай ханышасы” келбес сапарга кеткен. (...” The Queen of Alai”, who has a great role in Kyrgyz politics and diplomacy, passed away 111 years ago.) (Kaza bolgonuna 111 jyl. Kurmanjan datka tuuraluu 13 fakty, 2018).

7. «Нарын дарыясынан крокодил табылды». Жапаров Иманалиевдин кылмыш иши бар экенин айтты. (“Crocodile found in Naryn river”. Japarov said that Imanaliev has a criminal record.) (Japarov Imanalievdin kylмыш ishi bar ekenin aitty, 2020).

8. Абыке-Көбөштүн урпактары элдин башын айлантып, Манас атабыздын сөзүн таластан окутпай жатат. (Descendants of Abyke-Kobosh are confusing people, and don’t let the words of our father Manas be recited.) (Stenogramma vystuplenia A. Atambaeva pered stipendiatami, 2017).

3. Results and Analysis of the Survey

Overall 100 respondents took part in the survey, among them 17.2 % is 15 to 17 year old students, 49.5 % is 19 to 45 year old youth, 23.7 % is 46 to 59 year old middle aged people and 9.7 % is older people.

77.9 % female and 22.1 % male respondents answered the questionnaire, 55.8 % of respondents live in the city, 40 % of which live in the villages while 5.2 % live in small towns.

Multiple choice questions were asked to respondents, the authors avoided open-ended questions. Even though 100 persons participated in the survey some questions were skipped by them. After classic demographic questions, questions for precedent phenomena came.

The first question for a precedent name was asked without the context i.e. not presented as in media.

1. Do you know who Robin Hood was?

Do you know who Robin Hood was?

93 replies

82.8 % answered correctly. A folklore character that stole from the rich and gave to the poor was later featured in literature, cinema and theatre that it became widely known by everybody. In the Kyrgyz media current Robin Hood was used to describe the situation where some people collected money from ordinary people and helped those who were in need on behalf of themselves during Pandemic.

The second question for a precedent statement where the statement made by a great Kyrgyz writer Ch. Aitmatov who used a popular Greek poet's name was asked indirectly.

2. Who is "Homer of XX century" spoken about?

Who is "Homer of XX century" spoken about?

95 replies

76.8 % of respondents answered correctly. Homer of XX century is a great Kyrgyz improviser of epic "Manas" Sayakbai Karalaev. The popular epic "Manas" recited by S.Karalaev consists of 500 000 lines.

In the third question for a precedent text a short sentence from Internet media was given to learn who the person was spoken about.

3. ...the "Iron Lady's" health worsened, she resigned and refused to participate in social and political events. Who is it about?

...the "Iron Lady's" health worsened, she resigned and refused to participate in social and political events.
Who is it about?

94 replies

46.8% of respondents gave a correct answer while 28.7 % of respondents think that it is about Angela Merkel and 24.5 % of participants suggested that it was Aida Salyanova who was Prosecutor General and Minister of Justice of the Kyrgyz Republic.

In the fourth question for a precedent situation, a short sentence from Internet media was given to learn who the person was spoken about.

4. ... Britain's flexible "Iron Lady" promises to cut taxes and rein in Putin. Who is it spoken about?

... Britain's flexible "Iron Lady" promises to cut taxes and rein in Putin.
Who is it spoken about?

88 replies

For options an American talk show host, television producer, actress, author, and media proprietor Opra Winfrey, Michelle Obama who is a lawyer, writer, and the wife of the 44th President, Barack Obama and Mary Elizabeth Truss (born 26 July 1975) is a British politician who served as Prime Minister of the United Kingdom and Leader of the Conservative Party from September to October 2022 were given. 38.6 % of respondents marked that it is about Michelle Obama, 21.6 % chose Opra Winfrey while 39.8 % of participants gave a correct answer pointing Liz Truss. This might be explained with the fact that she was a prime-minister of UK for a short period of time. It should be pointed out that out of 100 respondents only 88 of them answered the rest just skipped the question.

The fifth question where a national precedent name for a certain historical personality was asked and 95.7 % of respondents answered correctly.

5. Who do you know Kurmandjan datka as?

Who do you know Kurmandjan datka as?

94 replies

4.3% of participants think that her heart is the lion heart that she is brave. 95.7 % of respondents marked her as a Queen of Alai. She contributed much in the 19th century uniting the Kyrgyz tribes and making a peace with the Russian Empire.

6. The sixth question for a national precedent text sounded what does “a crocodile was found in Naryn River” mean for you?

What does “a crocodile was found in Naryn River” mean for you?

94 replies

To the surprise of authors, only 35.1 % of respondents marked the correct answer while 50 % marked the nonsense. An ex deputy and ex minister of education Kanybek Imanaliev marked that ‘trying to detect crime committed by me means finding a crocodile in the river Naryn’. Crocodiles don’t live in KG consequently it is impossible to detect any crime carried out by him. Later on in mass media an article called a crocodile was found in the river Naryn was published where his own words were used. Logically respondents might be right because if crime was detected he would be imprisoned but this didn’t happen.

7. The seventh question for a national situation where epic characters and their situation was used is perceived by people very well.

Who do you understand under descendants of Abyke Kobosh are confusing people?

94 replies

In the epic “Manas” close relatives betrayed the hero Manas and when an unpleasant incident happened in the Talas region in 2017, this event was evaluated as a betrayal by ex president, Almazbek Atambaev as in the epic. He expressed it in his speech at the ceremony of Presidential Scholarship awarding to successful students.

8. The last question for a precedent statement includes the statement that is more confusing. “Ask not what your country can do for you - ask what you can do for your country.” Which politician said this?

“Ask not what your country can do for you - ask what you can do for your country.”

Which politician said this?

92 replies

47.8 % of respondents marked correctly that it was ex president of the USA John Kennedy while 45.7% thought that it was ex-president of KR Almazbek Atambaev. On 31 August, 2012, on Independence Day speech ex-president Almazbek Atambaev used the statement, expressed by 35th President of USA JFK in 1961. He didn't refer in his speech therefore most people think that it's his words.

Conclusion

Among the news items where precedent phenomena were used, 80 % of presented news taken for analysis reflected politics. Having analyzed the results of the survey, the authors are convinced once more that any ordinary Kyrgyz person perceives national precedent phenomena. The fact that half of surveyed respondents marked that “Ask not what your country can do for you - ask what you can do for your country” had been stated by Almazbek Atambaev is because ex-president said this without mentioning whose statement it was. This can be explained with the fact that people living in rural areas might not be interested in politics and most of them might be politically illiterate. Moreover, still background knowledge of each person plays a great role. They heard Atambaev's speech and believed that it was his own words.

It was highlighted by linguists that any fully developed contemporary homo sapiens may recognize universal precedent phenomena, which are a component of humanity's universal cognitive space. But two examples for precedent phenomena of international layers got less than 50 %. They were Margaret Thatcher and Elizabeth Truss. This might be understood that not everyone who was surveyed was good at politics and history. Schoolchildren, youth and middle-aged people marked the well-known contemporaries. Given the full context or while reading Internet media contents they are certain to understand and perceive everything written there.

Having analysed the precedent phenomena awareness of Kyrgyz community, it can be concluded that various approaches should be made and methodology used to explain linguocultural and cognitive nature of complex phenomenon of precedence.

References

- Gudkov, D. B. (2003). *Teoria i praktika mejkulturnoi kommunikatsii*. Gnosis.
- Iyilcheek temir ayim. Liz Truss – Britaniyanyn jany premier-ministri. (2022). Retrieved November 26, 2023, from <https://www.bbc.com/kyrgyz/world-62769084>
- Japarov Imanaliev din kylmysh ishi bar ekenin aitty. (2020). Retrieved November 26, 2023, from <https://ky.kloop.asia/2020/11/24/>
- Karaulov, Yu. N. (2010). *Russkii iazyk i iazykovaya lichnost*. Editorial URSS.

- Kaza bolgonuna 111 jyl. Kurmanjan datka tuuraluu 13 fakty. (2018). Retrieved November 27, 2023, from <https://sputnik.kg/20180201/kurmanzhan-datka-tuuraluu-13-fakty-1037544592.html>
- Krasnych, V. V, Gudkov, D. B, Zaharenko, I. V. and Bagaeva, D. B. (1997). Kognitivnaya baza i pretsedentnye fenomeny v sisteme drugih edinitis i v kommunikatsii. *Vestnik Moskovskogo Universiteta*, 9(3), 62-85.
- Krasnych, V. V. (2006). *Etnopsiholingvistika i lingvokulturologia*. RGB.
- Kyrgyz koomu özübüzdü emes, özgönü künöölöp köngön elbiz. (2020). Retrieved November 27, 2023, from <https://kadam-media.kg/69152/>
- Stenogramma vystuplenia A. Atambaeva pered stipendiatami. (2017). Retrieved November 28, 2023, from <https://www.for.kg/news-454131-ru.html>
- Eki jüzdüülükpü je jüzü karalykpy? (2012). Retrieved November 26, 2023, from http://www.sayasat.kg/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=20216&catid=9&lang=kg&Itemid=104&limitstart=0
- “Temir ayim” Margaret Thatcher. (2013). Retrieved November 26, 2023, from <https://www.super.kg/article/show/21687>
- 20-kylymdun Gomeri. (2019). Retrieved November 26, 2023, from <http://nlkr.gov.kg/news/20-kylymdyn-gomeri/>

Çalışmanın yazarları “COPE-Dergi Editörleri İçin Davranış Kuralları ve En İyi Uygulama İlkeleri” çerçevesinde aşağıdaki hususları beyan etmişlerdir:

Etik Kurul Belgesi: Bu çalışma için etik kurul belgesi gerekmemektedir. / **Ethics Committee Approval:** Ethics committee approval is not required for this study.

Finansman: Bu çalışma için herhangi bir kurum veya kuruluştan destek alınmamıştır. / **Funding:** No support was received from any institution or organization for this study.

Destek ve Teşekkür: Çalışmanın araştırılması ve yazımı esnasında destek veya fikirlerine başvuru herhangi bir kişi bulunmamaktadır. / **Support and Acknowledgments:** There is no person whose support or ideas are consulted during the research and writing of the study.

Çıkar Çatışması Beyanı: Bu makalenin araştırması, yazarlığı veya yayınlanmasıyla ilgili olarak yazarların potansiyel bir çıkar çatışması yoktur. / **Declaration of Conflicting Interests:** The authors has no potential conflict of interest regarding research, authorship or publication of this article.

Yazarın Notu: Bu çalışma herhangi bir bildiri veya tezden üretilmemiştir. / **Author’s Note:** This study was not produced from any report or thesis.

Katkı Oranı Beyanı: Bu makalenin tüm bölümleri iki yazar tarafından hazırlanmıştır. / **Author Contributions:** All sections of this article have been prepared by two authors.